

RTO, A Specific Crop Ontology for Rice Trait Concepts

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2022/07/14

<http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology/>

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1. Introduction

2. Necessity

3. Rice Trait Ontology Construction

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6. Summary

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Introduction

- Collecte **rice trait phenotypic** concepts among plant ontologies
- Developpe an integrated **rice trait ontology**
- Provide **data service** for related researches

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Necessity

The quantity of PubMed rice literatures from 2000 to 2022

Studies on Crop Traits

Ontology name	Knowledge domain	Source URL
Plant Ontology (PO)	plant structures and developmental stages	http://browser.planteome.org/amigo
Plant Trait Ontology (PTO)	plant traits	http://browser.planteome.org/amigo
Plant Experimental Conditions Ontology (PECO)	treatments and growth conditions used in plant science experiments	http://browser.planteome.org/amigo
Phenotypic Qualities Ontology (PATO)	qualities and attributes	https://github.com/pato-ontology/pato
Wheat Trait Ontology (WTO)	Environmental condition and wheat traits	http://agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/WHEATPHENOTYPE

Necessity

- **Plant Trait Ontology (PTO)**

- Items: 1,554
- Information : **Class ID, Preferred Label, Synonyms, Definitions, Obsolete**, CUI, Semantic Types, Parents, database_cross_reference, definition, has_alternative_id, has_broad_synonym, has_exact_synonym, has_narrow_synonym, has_obo_format_version, has_obo_namespace, has_related_synonym, etc.

Preferred Label	Synonyms	Definitions	Obsolete
plant height	PTHT (related) shoot height (related) Ht (related)	A whole plant morphology trait (TO:0000398) which is the height of a whole plant (PO:0000003). Comment: Refers to: height (PATO_0000119): A 1-D extent quality inhering in a bearer by virtue of the bearer's vertical dimension of extension.	FALSE

Necessity

Why build the RTO when we already have the PTO?

- Rice has many **specific traits**

piricularia leaf spot

false smut

- There is **no** unified standard for rice traits
- Ontology specific for crops is developing, **but rice not**

Necessity

- **CO_320**
- **Information** : agronomic, morphological, physiological, quality, and stress traits

CO_320 [1438]

Rice Ontology

Curators

- Jeffrey Detras
- Frances Nikki Borja

Contributing scientists

- Kenneth McNally
- Ramil Mauleon
- Julie Mae Pasuquin
- William Eusebio
- Ruairadh Sackville Hamilton
- Cécile Grenier

Lead Center

Collaborators

Alliance

Necessity

- knowledge map of CO_320
- Example: Plant height

CO_320:0000076 (Plant height)

Parents:

CO_320:Morphological (Morphological)

Children:

CO_320:0000792 (Plant height average)

CO_320:0000479 (Plant height measurement)

CO_320:0000840 (PlntHt_Av_cm)

CO_320:0000839 (PlntHt_Meas_1to9)

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Rice Trait Ontology Construction

- **PTO:** Normalized plant trait conception included.
- **WTO:** Wheat trait conception and **environment condition** included.

Table 1. Main classes of WTO with the number of some subclasses

	No.
Environmental condition	221
Abiotic condition (e.g., chemical, nutrient, water, wind)	51
Biotic condition	171
Biotic stress	170
Disease	58
Bacterial disease	6
Fungal disease	44
Viral disease	6
Diseased caused by nematode	2
Pest	103
Insects	21
Plant property	374
Phenotype	45
Trait	326
Development (plant habit, precocity, vernalization)	19
Growth (crop yield, nutrient use efficiency, density)	41
Morphology (of awn, glume, grain, spike)	23
Quality	58
Food property	30
Grain composition	12
Grain quality	13
Milling quality	4
Reproduction	5,173
Response to environmental conditions	64
Response to abiotic stress	104
Response to biotic stress	

WTO, Wheat Trait Ontology.

Rice Trait Ontology Construction

As the figure shows, three strategies for ontology integration:

- **Merge**
- **Add**
- **Delete**

Rice Trait Ontology Construction

- Merge
75 nodes

Strategy: Map the same term in the other ontology to the **TO ID**.

e.g. **WTO: 0000095 nutrient deficiency** ----> **TO: 0000480 nutrient sensitivity**

Rice Trait Ontology Construction

- Add **118 nodes**

Strategy: Add the term which related to rice trait in WTO while does not appear in TO to TO, and **keep its WTO ID** and child nodes

e.g. **WTO:0000087 grain composition**

Rice Trait Ontology Construction

- Delete
63 nodes

Strategy: Delete the term not related to rice trait

e.g. **WTO:0000366** ~~wheat dwarf~~

Rice Trait Ontology Construction

- **RTO1.0** has completed the integration of WTO and TO
- **2,022** rice trait concepts included
- Download page:

<http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology>

RTO ontology hierarchy

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Rice Trait Ontology Web: <http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn/RiceTraitOntology>

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the Rice Trait Ontology website. The browser's address bar shows the URL <http://lit-evi.hzau.edu.cn>. The page features a search bar and a 'download' button. The main content is a table titled 'Rice Trait Ontology' with the following columns: ID, NAME, DEFINITION, and IS_A. The table lists 19 traits, including carbon sensitivity, epigenetic trait, alkali soil sensitivity, reversible male sterility, calcium sensitivity, sulfur sensitivity, potassium sensitivity, genic male sterility-photoperiod sensitive, magnesium sensitivity, nitrogen sensitivity, hydrogen sensitivity, resistance to disease by mycoplasma-like organism, panicle weight, oxygen sensitivity, cobalt sensitivity, plant morphology trait, boron sensitivity, and seedling height.

ID	NAME	DEFINITION	IS_A
TO:0000001	carbon sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the carbon content in the growth medi...	TO:0000252 ! non-mineral nutrient sensitivity
TO:0000002	epigenetic trait	"OBSOLETE. An epigenetic trait is a distinguishable f...	None
TO:0000003	alkali soil sensitivity	"Plant sensitivity to soils with alkali conditions (pH>7)...	TO:0000481 ! alkali sensitivity
TO:0000004	reversible male sterility	"Trait of a plant in which the action of the cytotoxic g...	TO:0000111 ! genetically engineered male sterility
TO:0000006	calcium sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the calcium content in the growth medi...	TO:0000251 ! secondary macronutrient sensitivity
TO:0000007	sulfur sensitivity	"Response by the plant in terms of sensitivity to sulfu...	TO:0000251 ! secondary macronutrient sensitivity
TO:0000008	potassium sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the potassium ion content in the growt...	TO:0000248 ! primary macronutrient sensitivity
TO:0000009	genic male sterility-photoperiod sensitive	"Male sterility affected by photoperiod." [Gramene:pa...	TO:0000199 ! genic male sterility
TO:0000010	magnesium sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the magnesium content in the growth ...	TO:0000251 ! secondary macronutrient sensitivity
TO:0000011	nitrogen sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the nitrogen content in the growth med...	TO:0000248 ! primary macronutrient sensitivity
TO:0000012	hydrogen sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the molecular hydrogen or hydrogen io...	TO:0000252 ! non-mineral nutrient sensitivity
TO:0000013	resistance to disease by mycoplasma-like organism	"An assay to determine the resistance exhibited by a ...	TO:0000242 ! microbial damage resistanceTO:00001...
TO:0000014	panicle weight	"Average weight of the panicle from the plants or tiller...	TO:0000583 ! infructescence weightTO:0000847 ! pa...
TO:0000015	oxygen sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the molecular oxygen or reactive oxyge...	TO:0000252 ! non-mineral nutrient sensitivityTO:0002...
TO:0000016	cobalt sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the cobalt content in the growth mediu...	WTO:0000463 ! heavy metal toxicityTO:0000247 ! oth...
TO:0000017	plant morphology trait	"A plant trait (TO:0000387) which is a morphological ...	TO:0000387 ! plant trait
TO:0000018	boron sensitivity	"Sensitivity to the boron content in the growth mediu...	WTO:0000331 ! metalloid toxicityTO:0000080 ! micro...
TO:0000019	seedling height	"Average height measurements of 10 seedlings, in ce...	TO:0000207 ! plant height

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Future Work

- Other ontologies will be integrated into RTO
- With the development of rice research, more rice trait need to be integrated into RTO
- RTO can be used to guide the knowledge discovery related to rice trait

The Roadmap of Rice Trait Ontology Construction

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Summary

- Provide a **standardized terminology set** of rice trait
- Benefit for **normalization** and **application** of rice trait
- Serve to automated rice **knowledge mining** and **experimental** guidance of rice breeding

Thank you!

Necessity

